

Sampling Station 1 Juwata Permai pond

Sampling Station 2 Pond behind the Airport

Sampling Station 3 Tengyun Pond

Sampling Station 4 Pond behind Islamic Center

Sampling Station 5 Tambak Mamburungan Pond

Map of Research Location: Traditional Fishponds in Tarakan City, North Kalimantan

Forms of microplastics found in pond waters: a) fiber, b) film, c) fragment, d) filament.

Colors of microplastics identified in the aquaculture pond waters of Tarakan City.
 Legend: a) black, b) brown, c) red, d) orange, e) blue, f) white, g) transparent, h) green.

Sample Extraction Process in Laboratory

